

IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY, GOVERNMENT AND ECONOMICS ARE INTERTWINED

Rajabboyev Botirjon

Student of Economics, Kokand University

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Annotation. The digital economy has both benefits and drawbacks. I highlight the critical role of government in ensuring that the digital economy runs effectively after presenting the benefits and possible difficulties brought about by the digital economy. Finally, I suggest a few areas where governments can focus their efforts in order to promote the healthy growth of the digital economy.

Key words. Digital economy, free digital products, data analysis (BDA) technologies, information friction, monetary worth of all final commodities.

Introduction. Great changes are occurring in our social and economic lives as a result of the rapid expansion of the digital economy. Consumers are receiving an increasing amount of free digital products and services, while AI and big data analysis (BDA) technologies deliver more tailored product suggestions, connecting suppliers and buyers more effectively. In the financial sector, these technologies also increase forecast accuracy and minimize information friction. However, they also pose a threat to privacy and data security. The accumulation of digital assets, particularly for platforms, can result in significant market power, opening the door to exploitative and discriminating behavior.

To balance the interests of all parties, prohibit inappropriate use of market power, and build efficient institutional and legal frameworks, government action is required.

This paper is broken into five portions for the rest of it. In the second half, I discuss four good consequences of the digital economy, and in the third section, I go through the issues that the digital economy has created that lie behind these advantages. I describe why government must play an active part in the digital economy in the fourth segment, and I propose some areas where governments can focus their efforts in the fifth section. I come to a conclusion in the last part.

The digital economy has improved people's well-being

The digital economy has a number of unique characteristics that are not seen in other forms of economies. Free goods and services such as Wikipedia, email services such as Gmail, and digital maps such as Google Maps are all part of the modern digital economy and have significant

economic value. They are unable to contribute to national accounts, however, because metrics such as GDP only evaluate the monetary worth of all final commodities having a price.

In the digital economy, data and the ability to create value through data become factors of production. This can include algorithms or the capability to analyze big data to produce value in various contexts. Although these factors are an important class of intangible assets, it is difficult to accurately measure the value of intangible assets beyond identifying their existence. However, studies about valuations in public markets all suggest that intangible assets are becoming an increasingly important component of valuation. There are several companies in the US with a valuation about a trillion dollars, while the biggest and most powerful bank in the United States is JP Morgan, with a market value of USD 200 billion. Belo et al. (2019) construct a generalized neoclassical model of investment with physical capital, quasi-fixed labor, and two types of intangible capital—knowledge and brand capital—as inputs. They find that the importance of physical capital for firm value has decreased in recent decades, while the importance of knowledge capital has increased, especially in high-tech industries, from 24.9% of total asset value in 1970 to 44.8% in 2010. This rising level of significance indicates that we must make progress in measuring intangible assets. We currently have a market measure of intangible assets, which is, in part the present value of these data- and digital-related assets in generating net revenue. However, there is no doubt that this measurement can be improved. Furthermore, we should note that intangible assets go well beyond what we would normally think of as intellectual property. Another distinctive feature of the digital economy is that information is ubiquitously available. The data factor is the core reference variable of investment decision-making in financial markets, playing an important role in reducing information friction. Zhu (2019) points out that recent computing advancements have enabled technology companies to collect real-time, granular indicators of fundamentals to sell to investment professionals. The introduction of this data increases price informativeness through decreased information acquisition costs and subsequently produces two effects on investors. On the one hand, managers have less of an opportunity to trade on their private information about future earnings when prices more accurately reflect these future earnings. On the other hand, data on firms' fundamentals can reveal recession trends in current business or the opportunity to achieve growth in the future, which can improve investment efficiency by guiding investors to reduce investment when the situation deteriorates and increase investment when opportunities expand. By identifying how signaling and search costs are reduced by big data analytics for credit risk management of P2P lending, Yan et al. (2015) also show how information asymmetry is reduced in the big data era. Breakthroughs in ICTs (information and communications technologies), such as big-data-based Fintech, have been identified as an important disruptive driving force in the lending industry. The big data era has witnessed significant changes in methods for collecting, presenting, and evaluating information. Search costs for credit information have been dramatically reduced, and the collection of credit data has shifted

from passive information retrieval to proactive information gathering. It is worth noting that these trends enable financial firms to provide services like credit to previously under-served populations. The importance of digital technologies to enhance the inclusiveness characteristics of markets should not be underestimated. From an economic point of view, the informational gaps and asymmetries that exist in almost all markets are being partially eliminated, which will come with significant positive features as well as potential challenges. Responsible data usage can create and drive markets that did not exist before. For example, one can extend credit to people who are virtually anonymous to the traditional banking system. This is very powerful and encourages inclusive economic growth. In the digital economy, the existence of more than one megaplatform is a sign of market health. However, the mega-platforms must sufficiently overlap. Both the US and China have a handful of major platforms: the US has Google, Amazon, and Facebook, while China has Tencent, Alibaba, JD.com, and Pinduoduo. In the US, Amazon is the mega-platform that is closest to Alibaba in structure, although the two companies still have significant differences. In the beginning, however, eBay and Alibaba were quite similar, and their paths of evolution were also quite alike. While eBay has now fallen behind, it was once the inspiration for every mega-platform in the world. The fundamental concept at eBay was the insight that a lot of potential markets don't exist simply because buyers and sellers cannot find each other, but on the World Wide Web, this can be remedied. Thus, mega-platforms learned to capture the most elementary feature of how to make a market, which is to provide a way for buyers and sellers to make contact. The story of eBay began with collectibles. There are people all over the world who collect very niche items, and though this market did exist prior to eBay, it was fragmented through dealers working in different categories of collectibles. When eBay was founded, it transformed the market by connecting buyers and sellers across all these different categories on a single platform. The story gets even more interesting because eBay realized that there was one major thing holding back their platform—a lack of trust. The buyers didn't believe the sellers would send the product, and the sellers didn't believe the buyers would send the money. Thus, PayPal came out of eBay to deal with this problem, even though credit cards were already widespread. Similarly, in Latin America, Mercado Pago was born out of Mercado Libre to deal with the same problem. In each case it was a payment system that wasn't really a payment system at the start—it was an escrow system. The digital technologies underlying today's mega-platforms are so powerful, in part, because they are closing informational gaps. Now buyers and sellers can find each other, and mega-platforms have found a way to deal with the trust problem, turning isolated markets and transactions into repeated transactions. Another component of solving the trust problem has been two-way evaluation systems on platforms like Airbnb. This changes the informational structure of the market as well as the incentive structure. If someone were to rent an apartment through an online platform and absolutely trash it, they would find it very difficult to rent through the same platform again. However, before the invention of such platforms, this information would have been lost and the perpetrator could have continued renting, perhaps leaving a path of trashed apartments in

their wake. Through evaluation systems, payment systems, and the enormous amount of data that can be collected, companies can find information and make inferences about people that would be impossible without such data, leading to more inclusive patterns. MyBank, for example, lends to businesses that might have as few as five employees. There are millions small companies, which are too small to deal with traditional banks as they have no collateral and limited accessible track records. As Bengt Holmstrom has observed, now, on financial mega-platforms, data has become the new collateral. The evolution of mega-platforms as described above is still underway and has been almost revolutionary in the way economies form and function. There are two important features of mega-platforms in particular that we should keep in mind: they have an enormous amount of market power, and they can be hubs in a network to support innovation. As mentioned in Section 2, data can generate useful information both for reducing inefficiency in financial markets and improving social welfare. On the other hand, breaches in data privacy and data security are also large risks. We must also note that there is a potential conflict between protecting privacy and generating publicly useful information. Data is most useful when it can be pooled and shared in a responsible ways. With the rapid development of ICT, the means and ability of companies to capture users' data have been greatly enhanced. Although consumers benefit from targeted product recommendations based on big data analysis, they also bear the monetary cost and negative utility caused by the violation of their personal privacy (Acquisti et al., 2016). A large proportion of big data analysis entails high-velocity data types such as those related to click-stream and GPS data from mobile devices, which can be used to make short-term predictions with a high level of accuracy (Kshetri, 2014). However, these kinds of data are highly sensitive, as their abuse can easily lead to problems related to consumer privacy and security. Nevertheless, a number of companies have engaged in questionable data collection and sharing practices, without adequate consent arrangements. Consumers have expressed growing concern over organizations' data collection methods, especially the use of tracking technologies, such as cookies and GPS trackers. While this data provides firms with a great deal of knowledge about consumer tastes, price sensitivities, and their distribution across the population through data analysis, most consumers generally lack awareness of the various aspects of firm offerings. This asymmetry may put consumers in a relatively disadvantaged position. Negative welfare effects are especially noted for consumers who are poor, uneducated, and technologically less informed. Some analysts have argued that firms' big data initiatives may affect the welfare of low-income and minority consumers more negatively.

Specific roles of the government in the digital economy

Different countries and cultures have different views about the role of government in the digital economy based on varying levels of trust in their governments. In the United States, lower levels of trust in the government cause people to push back when, for example, the FBI asks Apple

to help unlock an iPhone. In China, however, people have much more faith in their government, believing in many cases that the government is the only institution trustworthy enough to access certain batches of data or maybe even to have universal access to cloud computing systems. The general public has accepted that depending on the situation, the government will either be directly managing the data or will have the right to oversee and access it when needed. This has created favorable conditions for the Chinese government's intervention in the digital economy.

As for ecosystems, Silicon Valley, although it wasn't digital, provides a very good example of this phenomenon. One of the characteristics of Silicon Valley after it had developed for 20 or 25 years was that there were all kinds of complementary resources available to support entrepreneurs and innovation, all concentrated in one place. For example, if someone designed a semiconductor chip, it wasn't necessary to have the capacity to build it—there was someone else who could make a trial version and test it. Similarly, in finance, start-ups didn't have to know anything about finance or accounting because there were venture capitalists who could take care of that. This environment was designed to allow the innovators to focus on creating value by providing them with all of the resources necessary to bring their ideas to life. Something similar is occurring in the digital economy. There is a noticeable increase in entrepreneurial activity in much of the work. Unicorns are proliferating. At least some of this trend can be traced to the opportunities and low entry barriers in the digital economy. The platforms are part of this process. However, because these platforms are turbocharged with data, they can operate on a massive scale and a much broader front. Tencent is an example of a Chinese mega-platform with a massive amount of market power. As they misused this power in some areas, such as music streaming, the Chinese government recently intervened by imposing an administrative penalty in accordance with the law. The Chinese economy is so big that there are competing megaplatforms in various areas, such as mobile payment systems. When it comes to innovative fintech companies, JD.com and Pinduoduo are not as big as Alibaba, but they haven't been knocked out of the market either. Maybe this lesson doesn't apply to smaller economies, but smart regulation or oversight is justified in these cases, as controlling access to the market is a source of potential market power. However, we cannot expect all platforms to have the same responsible motivation as the above examples, nor can we expect existing megaplatforms to keep their intentions unchanged. As previously mentioned, the accumulation of ICT and digital capital in superstar firms has created brand new types of monopoly market power. When this power is abused, predatory and discriminatory pricing behavior will emerge, seriously hindering innovation activities. The government must limit this and ensure a healthy market with more than one mega-platform in order to guarantee consumer surplus and innovation dynamism. We must also consider that our DNA sequences are not just useful to the doctors treating us or to people who want to exploit them—they are also useful as part of a pool of data that can be used for research purposes. Individuals may not factor this into their decision-making as a benefit, which is striking as a kind of positive information or

knowledge-based externality. Therefore, my opinion is that although people have rights regarding the use of their data, they don't actually own it in the full-blown sense that they must be paid for its usage. It's hard to picture how the world could work if everyone literally owned their data, requiring a contract every time someone's data was used, even if they had allowed it to be used for a specific purpose. This is an issue that experts and governments have not quite sorted out yet. On a related note, there is a distributional problem as to whether people should benefit from the enormous value creation around the process of digitalizing the economy. Right now, firms are creating a massive amount of value with digital and intangible assets and relatively small numbers of people. Employment and value creation are separating, and the ownership of high-value assets is significantly concentrated. There is clearly a distributional problem but allowing people to own their data may not be the correct solution. In view of the conflict between personal privacy and the benefits from the nonrivalry of the data factor, in addition to the "digital privacy paradox" problem experienced by consumers (expressing concerns about data privacy but easily disclosing data in reality), it is not the best choice to completely hand over data property to either firms or consumers (Jones and Tonetti, 2020; Athey et al., 2017). Instead, the government should intervene in the distribution. Tene & Polonetsky (2012) propose that policymakers should address some of the most fundamental concepts of privacy law, including the definition of "personally identifiable information," the role of consent, and the principles of purpose limitation and data minimization in order to craft a balance between beneficial uses of data and the protection of individual privacy. Policymakers should engage with this normative question, consider which activities are socially acceptable, and spell out the default norms accordingly. In doing so, they should assess the value of data uses against potential privacy risks, examine the practicability of obtaining true and informed consent, and keep in mind the enforceability of restrictions on data flows.

Conclusion

As we enter the digital era, revolutionary innovations in the digital economy have significantly changed methods of production and ways of life. As a type of capital, digital intangible assets can tremendously improve the production efficiency and market value of companies. Big data analysis technology reduces information friction and increases prediction accuracy in financial markets, subsequently improving the efficiency of investment. In the public sector, the positive externality of data generates useful public information, guides public decision-making, and improves social welfare. Furthermore, bilateral digital mega-platforms can take advantage of their integrated user data to promote the efficiency of supply and demand matching. Nevertheless, the digital economy simultaneously generates a number of problems. The benefits of big data analysis sometimes come at the expense of violating users' privacy, while the free flow of data, information, and technologies causes national security concerns. Furthermore, the prevailing automation process in the digital economy generates a substitution effect on human beings, thus shocking the labor market. Digital

mega-platforms may also abuse their huge market power to conduct predatory and discriminatory pricing behavior, therefore damaging consumer surplus and innovation dynamism. The laissez-faire approach will not work for the digital economy. Rather, the government has an indispensable role to play—it must intervene in the name of equity and fairness as well as sociopolitical and social cohesion. Besides these distributional problems, there are many other problems that the market will not solve on its own without government intervention, including externality problems and informational gap problems. We need the government to supervise the market power of mega-platforms and encourage more innovation, craft an effective institutional and legal framework for the distribution of data property, and design an effective tax and incentive system for the digital economy. Finally, governments cannot afford to isolate themselves in the contemporary digital economy but must work together to meet the new challenges of the digital era.

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